

ND280++, a multi-ton upgrade of the near detector for Hyper-Kamiokande

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Physics motivations

- Long baseline neutrino experiments measure CP violation by comparing $P(\nu_\mu \rightarrow \nu_e)$ and $P(\bar{\nu}_\mu \rightarrow \bar{\nu}_e)$

- Searches of CP violation in neutrinos in T2K, SK, Nova
 - [T2K+SK](#) exclude CP conservation at 1.9σ , hinting at maximal CPV
 - [T2K+Nova](#) also shows hints of $\delta_{CP} \neq 0$ depending on mass ordering

- Maximal CPV discovery at 5σ during the high-statistics HyperK era impacted by a **4% systematic uncertainty in $\sigma_{\nu_e}/\sigma_{\bar{\nu}_e}$**

- See [Robert Kralik's talk](#) for the status of HyperK

ND280

- ND280 is a near detector complex, 280m from the ν -beam origin generated at J-PARC's 30GeV proton accelerator in Tokai, Japan
 - Installed in 2010 for the T2K experiment
 - To be inherited by HyperK experiment as its ND in ~ 2028
- Off-axis at 2.5° for narrow energy band at FD

- Current configuration installed in April 2024 (“ND280+”)
 - Downstream detectors include Time Projection Chambers (TPCs) for tracking and Fine Grain Detectors (FGDs) as targets
 - FGD2 has the only (small) water target in ND280
- Newer upstream detectors:
 - SuperFGD
 - Two High-angle TPCs
 - Six Time of Flight panels

SuperFGD

- 2 tonne target of optically separated plastic scintillator cubes
- Improved low momentum proton efficiency
- 4π angular acceptance

- ~ 2 million $1 \times 1 \times 1$ cm³ cubes
- 3D readout using WLS fibres, ~ 56 k channels

HyperKamiokande

- FD completion in 2028
 - Fiducial volume 8x larger than SK
 - Beam power: 750kW (T2K) \rightarrow 1.3MW
 - 1 year HK data \approx 20 years of T2K
- Intermediate water Cherenkov detector under construction
 - See backup slides
- HK will inherit ND280:

Neutron kinematics important for $\bar{\nu}$ interactions but many escape SFGD
 ↓
Need larger target

Scaling carbon interactions in ND to oxygen in FD will be a larger uncertainty
 ↓
More water target in ND280

δ_{CP} will be dominated by $\nu_e/\bar{\nu}_e$ in H_2O cross section uncertainties
 ↓
Need higher ND statistics

Proton threshold in the SFGD still misses half of tracks
 ↓
Need a target with better granularity

HK-ND280++

Reference for possible [ND280++ design](#) – not final

- R&D for ND upgrades underway:
 - Replace tracker region after 2030
 - New ND280+ detectors will remain
- **10 tonnes** available for new ideas
 - Large fraction for water
 - New vertical TPC
 - R&D for TPC optical readout at CEA Saclay
- Refurbished Electromagnetic Calorimeter
 - Replace MPPCs with latest available
- Expect $\sim 4000 \nu_e / 10^{21} \text{ POT}$ at 20% efficiency, comparable to IWCD
- See [Ewan Miller's talk](#) for more details on simulation and physics studies

Water-based Liquid Scintillator

- SFGD-like highly segmented WbLS detector with 3D readout
 - Maximize H₂O content
 - Light Yield > 10 p.e.
- Developing prototypes at LPNHE, ETH Zurich and Kyoto U
 - In collaboration with WbLS inventor M. Yeh (BNL) [NIM A 660, 51–56 \(2011\)](#), [JINST 19 P01003 \(2024\)](#)

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ETH prototype, submitted to JINST
[arXiv 2508.11355](#)

- For the ETH prototype:
 - Composition of 90% H₂O, 10% LS (LAB+PPO+MSB)
 - 3M and Divinycell for optical separation, >80% water by weight
- Average light yield over 6 channels for cosmic rays:

	<LY> per fiber	xtalk
LS	42.5 p.e.	2.3%
WbLS	6.0 p.e.	1.9%

- PID in organic scintillator can be done at lower light yield than the SFGD

WbLS at Kyoto U

- Studied different mixing ratios for the WbLS:

- Triton X-100, SDS, LAS, TERGITOL NP-10, BC as surfactants
- PC for solvent
- PPO as a fluorescent
- BisMSB as a wavelength shifter
- 70% water by weight
- PMMA as optical separator

Plastic scintillators for Super-FGD
WbLS cell
Plastic scintillators for Super-FGD

Kyoto U prototype,
[PTEP 2025 123H02](#)

- e^+ beam test at RARiS, light yield ~ 3 p.e./MeV, 5% Xtalk

- Improvements being studied:

- IGEPAL CO-630 as surfactant with more LS $\rightarrow 1.78 \times$ higher LY
- PTFE as an optical reflector $\rightarrow 1.5 \times$ higher LY
- 6 p.e./MeV possible (but aiming for >8)

Path forward with WbLS

- Aiming for LY > 10 p.e. to ensure good muon vs proton PID
- ETH is investigating
 - Higher bias voltage (increases PDE by ~20%)
 - Larger pixel pitch for MPPCs (increases LY by ~20%)
 - Increasing the number of WLS fibres (~60% higher LY, only 1% more plastic)

- At LPNHE, we are investigating
 - WLS fibre configurations
 - Reflective materials

- At LPNHE, 3D printed 8cm³ “SuperCube” with 3M reflector
 - Filled with SFGD cubes, LS or WbLS
 - 4 WLS fibres and SiPMs
 - Took measurements with Sr-90 beta source
- Median WbLS LY found to be ~5x lower than LS in early tests
 - Now working on improvements and comparative measurements (and simulations)

Developed LED calibration and analysis workflow

Inactive water

- Planes of scintillating fibres ($\sim 0.2\text{mm}$) in inactive water tracker
 - For 500 MeV γ , magnetic bending separates e^+e^- by 3mm over 15cm
 - Sci-Fi sheets provide mm-level granularity for $e^-/e^+/\gamma$
- Have fibres in orthogonal direction to sheet \rightarrow x/y position tracking
 - Useful for tracking short protons
- Ongoing R&D at Tohoku U for SiPMs, multiplexing and gluing fibre mats

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Scintillating fibres

- Scintillating fibres as an active target at ETH/Luxium
- Strong constraint on nuclear effects
- Tested with commercial 0.5mm diameter fibres
 - Also comparing with 0.25mm fibres
 - Even with 0.5 mm fibres, proton tracking down to 150 MeV/c was good
- Single-Photon avalanche diode array imaging sensors
- Low-cost readout for millions of SciFi

[EPJC 2924 84:202](#)

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Conclusion

- During HyperK high statistics era (>2030), sensitivity to CPV will be dominated by cross section systematic uncertainties, mainly $\sigma_{\nu_e}/\sigma_{\bar{\nu}_e}$
- We are developing the conceptual design of ND280++ to reduce such cross section uncertainties and reduce the momentum detection thresholds of hadrons
 - Planning construction in the 2030s
 - New subdetectors being considered: Inactive water detector, 3D WbLS, SciFi, new TPC
 - Alternative configurations include a bigger plastic scintillator “HyperFGD”, organic scintillator for CH-compound subtraction/ ν -H sample selection, or opaque liquid scintillator
 - See [Ewan Miller's talk](#)
- ND280++ is a unique opportunity for new institutions to join HyperK with exciting physics studies and R&D

Back up

Acronyms

- LAB: Linear Alkyl Benzene
- PPO: Primary solute 2,5-diphenyloxazole
- bisMSB: p-bis-(o-methylstyryl)-benzene
- PC: pseudocumene
- BC: benzethonium chloride
- LAS: linear-alkylbenzene-sulfonate
- PTFE: polytetrafluoroethylene
- PMMA: Poly(methyl methacrylate)

T2K

- Tokai 2 Kamioka taking neutrino data since 2010
- J-PARC's 30GeV proton beam $\rightarrow \nu_\mu (\bar{\nu}_\mu)$ beam at $\sim 800\text{kW}$
- ND280 and SK 2.5° off-axis \rightarrow narrower E_ν

$$\sin^2 \left(\Delta m_{ij}^2 \frac{L}{4E} \right)$$

Super-Kamiokande

Mt. Noguchi-Goro
2,924 m

Mt. Ikeno-Yama
1,360 m

Near Detectors

J-PARC

Neutrino Beam

1,700 m below sea level

295 km

IWCD

- Intermediate water Cherenkov detector 850m from ν beam origin
- Under construction
- 7m in diameter, 8m tall, fiducial mass 150 tonnes
- Can measure neutrino flux for different energy spectra over a range of $1.7^\circ - 4.0^\circ$

